

1 RHEA: an open-source Reproducible 2 Hybrid-architecture flow solver Engineered for 3 Academia

4 **Lluís Jofre** ²

5 ¹ Department of Fluid Mechanics, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya · BarcelonaTech (UPC),
6 Barcelona 08019, Spain ² Department of Computer Applications in Science & Engineering, Barcelona
7 Supercomputing Center, Barcelona 08034, Spain

DOI: [10.xxxxxx/draft](https://doi.org/10.xxxxxx/draft)

Software

- [Review](#)
- [Repository](#)
- [Archive](#)

Editor: [Patrick Diehl](#)

Reviewers:

- [@ctdegroot](#)
- [@thomasgillis](#)

Submitted: 24 June 2022

Published: unpublished

License

Authors of papers retain copyright
and release the work under a
Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
International License ([CC BY 4.0](#)).

8 Summary

9 The study of complex multiscale flows ([Groen et al., 2014](#)), like for example the motion
10 of small-scale turbulent eddies over large aerodynamic structures ([Jofre & Doostan, 2022](#)),
11 microconfined high-pressure supercritical fluids for enhanced energy transfer ([Bernades & Jofre,
12 2022](#)), or hydrodynamic focusing of microorganisms in wall-bounded flows ([Palacios et al.,
13 2022](#)), greatly benefits from the combination of interconnected theoretical, computational
14 and experimental approaches. This manifold methodology provides a robust framework to
15 corroborate the phenomena observed, validate the modeling assumptions utilized, and facilitates
16 the exploration of wider parameter spaces and extraction of more sophisticated insights. These
17 analyses are typically encompassed within the field of Predictive Science & Engineering ([Njam,
18 2009](#)), which has attracted attention in the Fluid Mechanics community and is expected
19 to exponentially grow as computational studies transition from (mostly) physics simulations
20 to active vectors for scientific discovery and technological innovation with the advent of
21 Exascale computing ([Alowayyed et al., 2017](#)). In this regard, the computational flow solver
22 presented aims at bridging the gap between studying complex multiscale flow problems and
23 utilizing present and future state-of-the-art supercomputing systems in academic environments.
24 The solver presented is named RHEA, which stands for *open-source Reproducible Hybrid-
25 architecture flow solver Engineered for Academia*, and is available as an open-source Git
26 repository at <https://gitlab.com/ProjectRHEA/flowsolverrhea>.

27 Statement of need

28 The computational study and optimization of multiscale flow problems, like for example
29 turbulence, requires the utilization of powerful supercomputers. In particular, the computational
30 cost of studying wall turbulence, in terms of total number of grid points N , by means of direct
31 numerical simulation (DNS) and/or wall-modeled large eddy simulation (LES) strategies scales
32 with the Reynolds number as $N \sim Re^{37/14}$ and $N \sim Re$ ([Choi & Moin, 2012](#)), respectively.
33 Therefore, flows at high Reynolds numbers require large computational meshes solved on
34 substantial node counts. As a result, the meshes used to discretize the computational domain
35 on which the equations of fluid motion are solved need to be partitioned (distributed) among
36 parallel tasks such that each of these only holds a local portion of the global mesh. The local
37 portion of each task is composed of a set of grid points that it owns, and a set of off-processor
38 grid points (owned by remote processors) connected with their corresponding local grid points.
39 This overlapped mesh partition is used to exchange data among nearest neighbors by means of
40 message passage interface (MPI) ([Forum, 2022](#)) instructions. In addition, present (and future)
41 supercomputers are equipped with accelerators, like for example graphics processing units

42 (GPU), interconnected with the central processing units (CPU) and the main memory at the
43 node level. In this regard, the flow solver RHEA uses OpenACC ([Organization, 2022](#)) pragmas
44 to efficiently speedup the main kernels. This computational framework has been designed
45 with the objective to facilitate the portability of the flow solver from small- and mid-size
46 workstations to top-tier supercomputers, while maintaining notable levels of computational
47 performance.

48 There is only a handful of full-fledged accelerated open-source flow solvers available in the
49 literature. Some selected examples for compressible flows include (i) popular multi-purpose
50 open-source packages for simulation ([Cantwell et al., 2015](#)) and design ([Economon et al., 2015](#)),
51 (ii) OpenSBLI ([Jacobs et al., 2017](#)) dedicated to the automated derivation of finite-difference
52 solvers for hybrid (CPU-GPU) architectures based on a Python framework, (iii) HTR ([Renzo et al., 2020](#))
53 constructed from the task-based Legion programming paradigm ([Stanford University, 2022](#))
54 and targeted to simulate hypersonic reacting flows, and (iv) STREAMS ([Bernardini et al., 2021](#))
55 resulting from the extension of a CPU-based solver to run on multi-GPU clusters and
56 focused on supersonic ideal-gas flows. In this regard, RHEA has been designed and developed
57 with the aim to cover this void for the academic community, specifically focusing on (i) solver
58 expressivity, (ii) generality of flow problems that can be studied in terms of thermodynamic and
59 flow regimes, (iii) rapid portability to different architectures, (iv) computational performance,
60 and (v) reproducibility through uploading to the repository the parameters and input files
61 required to regenerate the data from simulations.

62 Computational design

63 RHEA solves the three-dimensional (3-D) compressible equations of fluid motion utilizing
64 non-uniform Cartesian second-order discretizations ([Moin, 2010](#)) in combination with kinetic
65 energy preserving ([Coppola et al., 2019](#)) convection schemes, or different Harten-Lax-van-Leer-
66 type (HLL) Riemann solvers ([Toro, 2009](#)), and uses explicit Runge-Kutta methods ([Gottlieb et al., 2001](#))
67 for time integration. The set of conservation equations is closed by means of
68 ideal- or real-gas thermodynamics to target, respectively, subcritical and supercritical fluid
69 regimes ([Jofre & Urzay, 2021](#)). The solver can be utilized for a wide range of fluid mechanics
70 problems as it allows (i) to flexibly overwrite most high-level kernels to set, for example, specific
71 initial conditions and source terms, and (ii) select between Dirichlet, Neumann, periodic, and
72 subsonic & supersonic inflow-outflow ([Poinsot & Lele, 1992](#)) boundary conditions. RHEA
73 is written in C++ ([Stroustrup, 2013](#)), using object-oriented programming, utilizes YAML
74 ([YAML Web Site, 2022](#)) and HDF5 ([Group, 2022](#)) for input/output operations, and targets
75 hybrid (CPU-GPU) supercomputing architectures based on a state-of-the-art parallel and
76 scalable MPI ([Forum, 2022](#)) + OpenACC ([Organization, 2022](#)) accelerated (managed-memory)
77 computational framework.

78 The computational performance of RHEA is analyzed by carrying out performance and scalability
79 tests based on 100 time iterations of the 3-D turbulent channel flow configuration described
80 in the next section. In this regard, to assess the portability of RHEA to different computing
81 systems, the tests have been performed on (i) a local hybrid machine (results are referred to
82 as Hybrid) and (ii) the Barcelona Supercomputer Center ([Barcelona Supercomputing Center, 2022](#))
83 (results are indicated as BSC) without performing any particular tuning of the solver.
84 The Hybrid machine is composed of a node with 1 AMD Ryzen 9 3900XT 12-core CPU and
85 2 NVIDIA Quadro RTX 4000 GPUs, while the BSC supercomputer contains a CPU-GPU
86 cluster with 3 racks formed of 54 IBM POWER9 nodes, each containing 2 Witherspoons CPUs
87 (20 cores of 3.1 GHz each), 4 Volta NVIDIA GPUs (16 GB each), and 6.4 TB of NVMe
88 (Non-Volatile Memory). The number of grid points utilized for the strong (total quantity)
89 and weak (quantity per node) scalability tests correspond to $256 \times 256 \times 256$ (Hybrid) and
90 $384 \times 384 \times 384$ (BSC). Three main observations can be inferred from the results. First,
91 focusing on the time-to-solution when using CPUs+GPUs with respect to only CPUs, the
92 solver is accelerated approximately $2.5\times$ and $5\times$ on the Hybrid and BSC computers. Second,

93 as shown in Figure 1(left), on BSC for a fixed-problem size and noting that on CPUs+GPUs
 94 the solver is roughly $5\times$ faster, the solver presents strong scalability speedups above 80% and
 95 60%, respectively, when running on CPUs and CPUs+GPUs up to 32 nodes (640 cores and
 96 128 GPUs). Third, maintaining the same ratio of problem size to number of nodes, RHEA is
 97 able to preserve weak scalability efficiency above 90% on CPUs and CPUs+GPUs up to 32
 98 nodes on BSC as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Strong scalability speedup (left) and weak scalability efficiency (right) of RHEA on BSC supercomputer using CPUs and CPUs+GPUs.

99 Application example

100 The ability of RHEA to configure a wide range of computational flow problems and run them
 101 efficiently on powerful supercomputing systems is demonstrated by simulating the canonical
 102 3-D turbulent channel flow problem (Smits et al., 2011) on 2 nodes of the CTE POWER9
 103 cluster of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (Barcelona Supercomputing Center, 2022).
 104 The friction Reynolds number selected is $Re_\tau = u_\tau \delta / \nu = 180$, where $u_\tau = 1$ m/s is the
 105 friction velocity, $\delta = 1$ m is the channel half-height, and $\nu = \mu / \rho$ is the kinematic viscosity
 106 of the fluid with μ the dynamic viscosity and $\rho = 1$ kg/m³ the density. The Prandtl number
 107 of the problem is $Pr = c_p \mu / \kappa = 0.71$ with c_p the isobaric specific heat capacity, and the
 108 Mach number is $Ma = u_b / \sqrt{\gamma P_b / \rho} = 0.3$ with u_b and P_b the bulk velocity and pressure,
 109 respectively, and $\gamma = 1.4$ the heat capacity ratio. The mass flow rate in the streamwise
 110 direction is imposed through a body force equal to $\mathbf{f} = [\tau_w / \delta, 0, 0]^T$, where τ_w is the wall
 111 shear stress.

112 The computational domain is $4\pi\delta \times 2\delta \times 4/3\pi\delta$ in the streamwise (x), wall-normal (y),
 113 and spanwise (z) directions, respectively. The streamwise and spanwise boundaries are set
 114 periodic, and no-slip conditions are imposed on the horizontal boundaries (x - z planes). The
 115 KGP convection scheme (Coppola et al., 2019) is utilized for solving the transport equations
 116 together with a third-order Runge-Kutta time-integration method. The grid is uniform in
 117 the streamwise and spanwise directions with resolutions in wall units equal to $\Delta x^+ = 9$ and
 118 $\Delta z^+ = 6$, and stretched toward the walls in the vertical direction with the first grid point
 119 at $y^+ = y u_\tau / \nu = 0.1$ and with sizes in the range $0.2 \lesssim \Delta y^+ \lesssim 4$. This grid arrangement
 120 corresponds to a DNS of size $256 \times 128 \times 128$ grid points. The simulation strategy starts
 121 from a linear velocity profile with random fluctuations (Nelson & Fringer, 2017), which is
 122 advanced in time utilizing the KGP convection scheme (Coppola et al., 2019) with CFL = 0.9
 123 to reach turbulent steady-state conditions after approximately 20 flow-through-time (FTT)
 124 units; based on the bulk velocity u_b and the length of the channel $L_x = 4\pi\delta$, a FTT is defined
 125 as $t_b = L_x / u_b \sim \delta / u_\tau$. Flow statistics are collected for roughly 30 FTTs once steady-state
 126 conditions are achieved, and compared against reference results (Moser et al., 1999).

Figure 2: Comparison against reference results of the time-averaged streamwise velocity u^+ (left) and velocity fluctuations u_{rms}^+ , v_{rms}^+ and w_{rms}^+ (right) along the wall-normal direction y^+ in wall units.

127 The time-averaged mean streamwise velocity u^+ and root-mean-squared (*rms*) velocity
 128 fluctuations u_{rms}^+ , v_{rms}^+ , w_{rms}^+ along the wall-normal direction y^+ in wall units provided by
 129 RHEA and compared to reference results (Moser et al., 1999) are depicted in Figure 2. As
 130 shown in the figure, the results from RHEA accurately reproduce the first- and second-order
 131 flow statistics by (i) properly capturing the inner (viscous sublayer, buffer layer and
 132 log-law region) and outer layers, and (ii) the flow fluctuations peaking around $y^+ \approx 15$ for the
 133 streamwise velocity. Additionally, a snapshot of the instantaneous streamwise velocity in wall
 134 units u^+ on a x^+ - y^+ slice is displayed in Figure 3 to provide qualitative information of the
 135 wall-bounded turbulence computed by RHEA.

Figure 3: Snapshot of the instantaneous streamwise velocity u^+ on a x^+ - y^+ slice from RHEA.

Acknowledgements

136 This work is supported by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's
 137 Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (grant agreement No. 101040379 -
 138 SCRAMBLE), and the *Beatriz Galindo* programme (Distinguished Researcher, BGP18/00026)
 139 of the *Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades* (Spain).
 140

References

142 Alowayyed, S., Groen, D., Coveney, P. V., & Hoekstra, A. G. (2017). Multiscale computing in
 143 the Exascale era. *J. Comput. Sci.*, 22, 15–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2017.07.004>
 144 Barcelona Supercomputing Center. (2022). *BSC-CNS | Barcelona Supercomputing Center.*
 145 <https://www.bsc.es>

- 146 Bernades, M., & Jofre, L. (2022). Thermophysical analysis of microconfined turbulent flow
147 regimes at supercritical fluid conditions in heat transfer applications. *J. Heat Transfer*, *144*,
148 082501. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4054554>
- 149 Bernardini, M., Modesti, D., Salvatore, F., & S.Pirozzoli. (2021). STREAmS: A high-fidelity
150 accelerated solver for direct numerical simulation of compressible turbulent flows. *Comput.*
151 *Phys. Commun.*, *263*, 107906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2021.107906>
- 152 Cantwell, C., Moxey, D., Comerford, A., Bolis, A., Rocco, G., Mengaldo, G., Grazia, D. D.,
153 Yakovlev, S., Lombard, J.-E., Ekelschot, D., Jordi, B., Hu, H., Mohamied, Y., Eskilsson,
154 C., Nelson, B., Vos, P., Biotto, C., Kirby, R., & Sherwin, S. (2015). Nektar++: An
155 open-source spectral/hp element framework. *Comput. Phys. Commun.*, *192*, 205–209.
156 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2015.02.008>
- 157 Choi, H., & Moin, P. (2012). Grid-point requirements for large eddy simulation: Chapman's
158 estimates revisited. *Phys. Fluids*, *24*, 011702. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3676783>
- 159 Coppola, G., Capuano, F., Pirozzoli, S., & Luca, L. de. (2019). Numerically stable formulations
160 of convective terms for turbulent compressible flows. *J. Comput. Phys.*, *382*, 86–104.
161 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2019.01.007>
- 162 Economou, T., Palacios, F., Copeland, S., Lukaczyk, T., & Alonso, J. (2015). An open-source
163 suite for multiphysics simulation and design. *AIAA J.*, *54*, 828–846. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.J053813>
- 164
- 165 Forum, T. M. (2022). *Message Passing Interface*. <https://www.mpi-forum.org>
- 166 Gottlieb, S., Shu, C.-W., & Tadmor, E. (2001). Strong stability-preserving high-order
167 time discretization methods. *SIAM Review*, *43*, 89–112. <https://doi.org/10.1137/S003614450036757X>
- 168
- 169 Groen, D., Zasada, S. J., & Coveney, P. V. (2014). Survey of multiscale and multiphysics
170 applications and communities. *Comput. Sci. Eng.*, *16*, 34–43. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2013.47>
- 171
- 172 Group, T. H. (2022). *Hierarchical Data Format 5*. <https://www.hdfgroup.org>
- 173 Jacobs, C., Jammy, S., & Sandham, N. (2017). OpenSBLI: A framework for the auto-
174 mated derivation and parallel execution of finite difference solvers on a range of computer
175 architectures. *J. Comput. Sci.*, *18*, 12–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2016.11.001>
- 176 Jofre, L., & Doostan, A. (2022). Rapid aerodynamic shape optimization under uncertainty
177 using a stochastic gradient approach. *Struct. Multidiscipl. Optim.*, *65*, 196. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00158-022-03293-y>
- 178
- 179 Jofre, L., & Urzay, J. (2021). Transcritical diffuse-interface hydrodynamics of propellants in
180 high-pressure combustors of chemical propulsion systems. *Prog. Energ. Combust.*, *82*,
181 100877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2020.100877>
- 182 Moin, P. (2010). *Fundamentals of engineering numerical analysis* (2nd ed.). Cambridge
183 University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511781438>
- 184 Moser, R. D., Kim, J., & Mansour, N. N. (1999). Direct numerical simulation of turbulent
185 channel flow up to $Re_\tau = 590$. *Phys. Fluids*, *11*, 943. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.869966>
- 186 Nelson, K. S., & Fringer, O. 4B. (2017). Reducing spin-up time for simulations of turbulent
187 channel flow. *Phys. Fluids*, *29*, 105101. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4993489>
- 188 Njam, H. N. (2009). Uncertainty quantification and polynomial chaos techniques in compu-
189 tational fluid dynamics. *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, *41*, 35–52. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.fluid.010908.165248>
- 190
- 191 Organization, T. O. (2022). *Open Accelerators*. <https://www.openacc.org>

- 192 Palacios, C., Jofre, M., Jofre, L., Romeu, J., & Jofre-Roca, L. (2022). Superheterodyne
193 microwave system for the detection of bioparticles with coplanar electrodes on a microfluidic
194 platform. *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, *71*, 8002910. [https://doi.org/10.1109/TIM.2022.](https://doi.org/10.1109/TIM.2022.3165790)
195 [3165790](https://doi.org/10.1109/TIM.2022.3165790)
- 196 Poinso, T. J., & Lele, S. K. (1992). Boundary conditions for direct simulations of compressible
197 viscous flows. *J. Comput. Phys.*, *101*, 104–129. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991\(92\)](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991(92)90046-2)
198 [90046-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991(92)90046-2)
- 199 Renzo, M. di, Fu, L., & Urzay, J. (2020). HTR solver: An open-source Exascale-oriented
200 task-based multi-GPU high-order code for hypersonic aerothermodynamics. *Comput. Phys.*
201 *Commun.*, *255*, 107262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2020.107262>
- 202 Smits, A. J., McKeon, B. J., & Marusic, I. (2011). High-Reynolds number wall
203 turbulence. *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, *43*, 353–375. [https://doi.org/10.1146/](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-fluid-122109-160753)
204 [annurev-fluid-122109-160753](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-fluid-122109-160753)
- 205 Stanford University. (2022). *Legion Programming System*. <https://legion.stanford.edu>
- 206 Stroustrup, B. (2013). *The C++ programming language* (4th ed.). Addison-Wesley.
- 207 Toro, E. F. (2009). *Riemann solvers and numerical methods for fluid dynamics* (3rd ed.).
208 Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/b79761>
- 209 YAML Web Site, T. Official. (2022). *YAML: YAML Ain't Markup Language*. <https://yaml.org>

DRAFT